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Review Paper

Smart Nanocarriers for Targeted Chemotherapy: A Review on Tumor Microenvironment-Sensitive Delivery Systems

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ABSTRACT

Conventional chemotherapy often represents a trade-off between specificity, systemic toxicity, and multidrug resistance, yielding suboptimal therapeutic benefits. Therefore, smart nanocarriers offer hope in delivering anticancer drugs directly to tumor sites in response to certain biological stimuli in the tumor microenvironment (TME), such as acidic pH, hypoxia, redox conditions, and enzyme overexpression. This review elaborates on the TME structure and barriers, stimuli-responsive nanocarrier systems including pH-, enzyme-, redox-, and hypoxia-sensitive types, and the materials used for their construction. Passive- and active-targeting strategies are also discussed, in addition to the most recent developments in clinical and preclinical settings. Additionally, this paper covers toxicity issues, regulatory concerns, and the opportunities to combine these systems with AI and theranostics. Smart nanocarriers essentially form a stepping stone toward personalized, effective cancer treatment with targeted delivery, fewer side effects, and higher therapeutic precision.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Cancer continues to take the major toll worldwide on morbidity and mortality. Even in the era of modern diagnostics and therapies, chemotherapy still remains a major route for treating several cancers [1]. Unfortunately, due to a lack of specificity, chemotherapy drugs tend to have grave side effects, besides their marginal therapeutic efficacy. As such, the idea of directing drugs to particular cells has gained ground in recent years, especially with the development of smart nanocarriers that can respond to specific tumor microenvironment (TME) stimuli [2]. This review extensively covers the tumor-responsive nanocarriers, design strategies, materials involved, and their usefulness in chemotherapy with respect to improved specificity and safety [3].

1.1 Overview of Chemotherapy Challenges

Conventional chemotherapy normally involves systemic administration of agents capable of killing both cancer and healthy cells. Due to this lack of selectivity, undesired effects appear, of which myelosuppression, gastrointestinal distress, and alopecia are the most common [4]. Besides, these drugs lose their therapeutic value under drug resistance mechanisms, such as pump effectors, DNA repairs, or altered path for apoptosis. Furthermore, poor localization of drugs at the tumor site, due to physiological barriers or rapid systemic clearance, is another major problem. Such drawbacks call for innovative approaches that can promote the therapeutic outcome and reduce toxicity at the same time [5].

1.2 Importance of Targeted Drug Delivery

With the goal of targeted delivery, drug delivery systems act to concentrate the chemotherapeutic agent at the site of the tumor, thus increasing efficacy while reducing systemic side effects. These strategies include passive targeting-from the

Enhanced Permeability and Retention (EPR) effect-to active targeting, which exploits ligands to bind to tumor-specific receptors [6]. Smart nanocarriers further offer the possibility of controlled drug release upon exposure to internal stimuli such as pH, enzyme presence, or redox potential, or external stimuli like light, heat, or magnetic fields. Such stimulus-responsive release limits toxic side effects toward healthy tissues and enables increased effective drug concentrations at the desired tumor site [7].

1.3 Role of Tumor Microenvironment (TME) in Cancer Therapy

TME is essential for cancer progression and therapeutic resistance.

It consists of a dense network of cancer cells, stromal cells, immune cells, blood vessels, extracellular matrix (ECM), and cytokines. Importantly, the TME exhibits distinctive physicochemical properties like acidic pH, hypoxia, increased levels of particular enzymes (e.g., matrix metalloproteinases), and redox imbalance [8]. These aberrations may be leveraged to create stimuli-responsive nanocarriers that release drugs preferentially within the tumor. Knowledge and targeting of the TME not only enhance drug delivery efficiency but also overcome mechanisms of therapy resistance inherent in cancer biology [9].

2. TUMOR MICROENVIRONMENT (TME): BIOLOGY AND BARRIERS

Tumor microenvironment (TME) is a dynamic, heterogeneous environment of tumor cells that is vital for the development, growth, metastasis, and treatment response of cancer. The TME differs from normal

tissues in consisting of a malformed extracellular matrix (ECM), aberrant vasculature, stromal cells, immune infiltrates, and signalling molecules [10]. Apart from sustaining tumor survival, these elements are also responsible for resistance to therapy and immune evasion. Knowing the biology and barriers of the TME is critical for the development of smart nanocarriers capable of navigating and adapting to this toxic environment. [11]

2.1 Structure and Components of TME

TME is a comprehensive network of both cellular and non-cellular constituents. Cellular components are cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs), tumor-associated macrophages (TAMs), myeloid-derived suppressor cells (MDSCs), endothelial cells, and immune cells. These cells communicate with tumor cells through signaling pathways that enhance angiogenesis, proliferation, and immune suppression [12]. The non-cellular matrix comprises ECM proteins (collagen, fibronectin), growth factors, and cytokines that form a scaffold for the growth of tumor cells. Such structural arrangement not only sustains cancer cell growth but also forms physical and biological barriers that restrict the effectiveness of conventional treatments [13].

2.2 pH, Enzymes, and Hypoxia in TME

One of the characteristics of TME is that it has acidic pH (~6.5–6.8) due to high glycolysis and compromised perfusion, contrasting the physiological pH of normal tissues (~7.4). Hypoxia, through abnormal and leaky vasculature, further changes the metabolic landscape and enhances therapy resistance. There are high concentrations of enzymes like matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), cathepsins, and hyaluronidase in the

TME, and they are responsible for ECM degradation and invasion of the tumor [14]. These biochemical markers are ideal internal stimuli for smart nanocarriers to facilitate site-specific release of drugs, making targeted chemotherapy more effective [15].

2.3 Barriers to Drug Penetration

The TME offers several obstacles to drug delivery. The compact extracellular matrix inhibits diffusion, and high interstitial fluid pressure (IFP) due to leaky vasculature and inadequate lymphatic drainage inhibits effective transport of therapeutic agents. Further, aberrant blood vessels cause irregular distribution of the drug, and acidic and hypoxic conditions can incapacitate some drugs [16]. Cellular elements such as CAFs and TAMs may also sequester drugs or induce resistance mechanisms. Overcoming these obstacles is essential to ensure that nanocarriers are delivered to their target and release their payload efficiently within the tumor tissue [17].

3. SMART NANOCARRIERS: AN OVERVIEW

Smart nanocarriers constitute a new frontier in drug delivery technology, engineered to respond to certain internal or external cues for targeted and controlled release of therapeutic drugs. Nanocarriers increase the accuracy of chemotherapy by stabilizing drugs, reducing off-targeted effects, and maximizing drug concentration at tumor locations [18].

Their activity is usually designed to capitalize on the distinctive features of the tumor microenvironment (TME), e.g., pH, enzyme level,

redox state, and hypoxia. The development of smart nanocarriers marks an evolution away from passive drug delivery towards active, environment sensing approaches for enhancing clinical success [19].

3.1 Definition and Classification

Intelligent nanocarriers are nanoscale drug delivery vehicles designed to release drugs upon certain stimuli in the diseased tissue or on external input [20].

They may be categorized according to the nature of stimulus they can respond to

Fig 1: Type of stimulus

These groups provide versatility in the designing of customized therapies for different kinds of cancers and phases.

3.2 Advantages over Conventional Carriers

Smart nanocarriers possess various benefits over regular drug delivery systems. They enhance site-specificity by releasing the drug under specific conditions only, minimizing systemic toxicity. Their stimuli responsiveness enables them to deliver the drug in a controlled and sustained manner, enhancing therapeutic efficiency. Smart carriers are capable of circumventing biological barriers like drug efflux

pumps and enhancing bioavailability of sparingly soluble drugs [21]. Most intelligent systems also maximize tumor penetration and retention, overcoming the shortcomings of common liposomes or micelles. Such qualities render them most appropriate for treating aggressive or resistant tumors where other treatments tend to fail [22].

3.3 Criteria for Smartness in Drug Delivery

A nanocarrier is "smart" if it satisfies certain conditions:

- Stimuli-sensitivity: It should have the ability to respond to one or more stimuli, for example, pH or enzyme action, with high selectivity.

- **Targeting capability:** Smart carriers should have ligands or surface alterations for active targeting towards tumor cells.
- **Stability in circulation:** It should be stable in the blood circulation to prevent premature drug release.
- **Controlled release behavior:** The release of drugs ought to be spatially (tumor location) and temporally (correct time) regulated.
- **Biocompatibility and biodegradability:** The materials employed must be safe and degradable to non-toxic by-products. These requirements assure smart nanocarriers deliver chemotherapy drugs effectively and safely [23].

4. STIMULI RESPONSIVE NANOCARRIERS FOR CHEMOTHERAPY

Stimuli-responsive nanocarriers are intelligent drug delivery systems designed to release the therapeutic agents in response to certain internal (e.g., pH, enzymes, redox condition) or external (e.g., temperature, light) stimuli. For cancer treatment, internal stimuli within the tumor microenvironment (TME) are of special interest because of their unique pathological characteristics [24]. These nanocarriers are stable under physiological conditions but selectively release their cargo at the tumor site, thus achieving maximum drug accumulation and minimum off-target toxicity. This section highlights some of the stimuli-responsive types of nanocarriers that are currently being explored for targeted chemotherapy [25].

Stimulus Type	Mechanism of Trigger	Common Materials/Linkers	Advantages
pH-Responsive	Cleavage/swelling under acidic pH (6.5-6.8)	Hydrazone, acetal, imine bonds, pH-sensitive polymers	Exploits tumor acidity, intracellular release
Enzyme-Responsive	Cleavage by tumor-overexpressed enzymes (MMPs, cathepsins)	Enzyme-cleavable peptides, MMP-sensitive polymers	High specificity, deep tumor penetration
Redox-Responsive	Disulfide bond cleavage by intracellular GSH	Disulfide linkers, redox-sensitive polymers	Stable in circulation, efficient intracellular release
Hypoxia-Responsive	Activation under low oxygen conditions	Nitroimidazoles, azobenzene linkers	Targets hypoxic tumor cores, overcomes resistance
Multi-Responsive	Response to multiple stimuli simultaneously	Combinations of above linkers/materials	Enhanced precision and control

4.1 pH-Responsive Nanocarriers

pH-sensitive nanocarriers take advantage of the acidic environment frequently present in the tumor extracellular matrix (pH ~6.5–6.8) and within

intracellular environments such as endosomes and lysosomes (pH ~4.5–6). These are typically constructed from pH-sensitive linkages or polymers that degrade or swell in acidic environments, releasing drugs [26]. Hydrazone, acetal, or imine bonds are representative examples that are stable at physiological pH but cleave in acidic environments.

This facilitates increased intracellular drug delivery of chemotherapeutic agents with less systemic side effects. pH-responsive systems are one of the most researched because of the uniform pH gradient between tumors and regular tissues [27].

4.2 Enzyme-Responsive Nanocarriers

Enzyme-responsive nanocarriers employ overexpressed TME enzymes—e.g., matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), cathepsins, or hyaluronidase—as the drug-release trigger. These nanocarriers contain enzyme-cleavable peptides or linkers that cleave specifically in response to target enzymes, allowing site-specific drug delivery. For instance, MMP-sensitive polymers disintegrate in tumor tissues, releasing targeted anticancer drugs. Enzyme-responsive systems improve the precision of targeting and can even enable tissue penetration and deep tumor delivery. They are most useful in metastatic or invasive cancers where enzyme activity is increased.

4.3 Redox-Responsive Nanocarriers

Redox-sensitive nanocarriers are formulated to respond to redox potential gradients between tumors and normal tissue. Cancer cells have high intracellular concentrations of the reducing agent glutathione (GSH), as much as 100–1000 times more than in the extracellular environment [28]. Disulfide moieties

that become cleaved in the reductive cell environment are present in many such carriers, causing rapid drug release in cancer cells.

Redox-sensitive systems provide dual advantages: blood circulation stability and effective intracellular drug delivery following cellular uptake. Redox-sensitive systems are most valuable for the improvement of cytotoxicity of drugs such as doxorubicin or paclitaxel [29].

4.4 Hypoxia-Responsive Nanocarriers

Hypoxia-sensitive nanocarriers are initiated by the low oxygen tension that typically occurs in fast-growing solid tumors. Hypoxia stimulates certain chemical functionalities (e.g., nitroimidazoles, azobenzene linkers) or triggers gene expression profiles that can be used for drug release. Such systems are especially valuable in targeting hypoxic cores of tumors, which tend to be refractory to traditional treatments [30]. Certain carriers even integrate hypoxia sensitivity with imaging or gene silencing for augmenting therapeutic efficacy. Hypoxia-responsive systems can enhance drug penetration and efficacy in otherwise inaccessible tumor tissues by taking advantage of oxygen-deprived areas [31].

4.5 Multi-Responsive Systems

Multi-responsive nanocarriers are engineered to respond to two or more stimuli in combination (e.g., pH + redox, enzyme + hypoxia) with the benefit of greater drug release control. The carriers allow for more accurate spatiotemporal drug delivery due to the need for multiple tumor-specific stimuli, which reduces the risk of premature release [32]. Multi-responsive systems commonly incorporate multiple functional materials or dual-cleavable linkers to counteract tumor heterogeneity

and enhance therapeutic index. For example, a nanocarrier can be stable in blood, start swelling in the acidic TME, and completely release its drug upon exposure to intracellular glutathione. Such sophisticated systems are the future generation of intelligent drug delivery technologies [33].

5. MATERIALS USED IN SMART NANOCARRIERS

The effectiveness of smart nanocarriers in targeted chemotherapy largely depends on the materials used

in their construction. These materials must be biocompatible, non-toxic, and capable of responding to specific stimuli such as pH, enzymes, or redox conditions [34]. Additionally, they should facilitate drug encapsulation, stability, and controlled release. Various organic, inorganic, and hybrid materials have been explored for this purpose, each offering unique structural, functional, and physicochemical advantages. This section discusses the most widely used materials in the development of smart nanocarriers for cancer therapy [34].

Material Type	Examples	Stimuli Responsiveness	Advantages	Applications
Polymeric Nanoparticles	PLGA, PEG, chitosan	pH, redox, enzyme	Biodegradable, tunable release profiles	pH/redox-responsive chemotherapy
Liposomes & Niosomes	Phospholipids, non-ionic surfactants	pH, enzyme	Biocompatible, versatile encapsulation	FDA-approved liposomal drugs
Dendrimers	PAMAM dendrimers	pH, redox	Precise architecture, multifunctional	Targeted delivery, gene therapy
Inorganic Nanoparticles	Gold, silica, iron oxide	External (light, magnetic), internal (pH)	Multifunctional, imaging + therapy	Photothermal therapy, theranostics
Hybrid Nanocarriers	Polymer-lipid, inorganic-organic hybrids	Multi-stimuli	Enhanced stability and targeting	Next-gen precision nanomedicine

5.1 Polymeric Nanoparticles

Polymeric nanoparticles represent one of the most versatile smart drug delivery platforms because they are tunable, biodegradable, and easily functionalizable. They are usually prepared from polymers such as PLGA (poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid)), PEG (polyethylene glycol), chitosan, or polyanhydrides [36]. Carriers can be designed to react to different internal stimuli by introducing pH-responsive, redox-

cleavable, or enzyme-degradable linkers. Polymeric nanoparticles have good stability, drug release profile control, and targeting tumor tissue through both passive and active means [37].

5.2 Liposomes and Niosomes

Liposomes are lipid bilayer spherical vesicles, whereas niosomes are analogous structures with non-ionic surfactants. Both are very biocompatible

and can entrap hydrophilic as well as lipophilic drugs [38]. Smart niosomes and liposomes can be functionalized using pH-sensitive lipids or enzyme-cleavable units to facilitate stimuli-responsive release of the drug. They also represent a great platform for surface functionalization with targeting ligands such as antibodies or peptides. FDA-approved liposomal pharmaceuticals (e.g., Doxil) paved the way for next-generation liposome-based intelligent delivery systems for cancer therapy [39].

5.3 Dendrimers

Dendrimers are branched, tree-shaped synthetic polymers with well-defined molecular architecture and many surface functional groups. Their defined architecture makes it possible for drugs, targeting moieties, and stimuli-responsive linkers to be attached to them. Dendrimers can enter tumor tissues effectively because they are in nanoscale and monodisperse [40]. Dendrimers are especially suitable for pH- and redox-responsive delivery systems, in which drug release can be sensitively regulated. Poly(amidoamine) (PAMAM) dendrimers are one of the most researched varieties and have been promising in the delivery of chemotherapeutic drugs with low toxicity [41].

5.4 Inorganic Nanoparticles (Gold, Silica, etc.)

Inorganic nanoparticles like gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs), iron oxide, and quantum dots provide distinct optical, magnetic, and structural characteristics. They can be designed to sense external stimuli such as light, heat, or magnetic fields or internal stimuli by surface modifications [42]. For instance, gold nanoparticles are capable of

absorbing near-infrared light to produce localized heat for photothermal therapy and at the same time release drugs. MSNs may be capped with stimuli-responsive gatekeepers that release drugs upon pH or enzyme-responsive release. Their hardness, high surface area, and multifunctionality render them useful for both diagnostic and therapeutic (theranostic) uses [43].

5.5 Hybrid Nanocarriers

Hybrid nanocarriers involve the mixture of two or more than two materials—like polymers and lipids or inorganic cores and organic shells—to couple the benefits of multiple systems. Hybrid nanocarriers can have improved stability, multi-stimuli responsiveness, and also better targeting efficiency. Like a polymer-lipid hybrid can provide the biocompatibility of liposomes and also the controlled release feature of polymers [44]. An inorganic-polymer hybrid could provide magnetic or optical imaging with drug delivery as well. Hybrid nanocarriers find particularly valuable applications in resolving the shortcomings of single-component systems and are regarded as next-generation precision chemotherapy platforms [45].

6. TARGETING STRATEGIES FOR TUMOR ACCUMULATION

Successful targeting of nanocarriers to the tumor site is essential to improve the therapeutic effect of chemotherapeutic drugs and reduce systemic toxicity. Tumor targeting methodologies are generally divided into passive, active, and biomimetic methods [46]. These methodologies utilize either the specific pathophysiological features of tumors or certain molecular interactions to achieve targeted delivery.

By enhancing localization and tumor site retention of nanocarriers, these processes play an important role in the success of intelligent drug delivery systems [47].

Targeting Strategy	Mechanism	Examples of Ligands/Cells Used	Advantages	Challenges
Passive Targeting (EPR)	Exploits leaky tumor vasculature	N/A	Simple, no modification needed	Variable EPR effect, tumor heterogeneity
Active Targeting	Ligand-receptor binding	Folate, RGD peptides, antibodies (HER2)	Enhanced specificity and uptake	Ligand selection, off-target binding
Biomimetic Targeting	Use of cell membranes or immune cells	RBC membranes, macrophages, cancer cell membranes	Immune evasion, homotypic targeting	Complex fabrication, scalability

6.1 Passive Targeting (EPR Effect)

Passive targeting exploits the Enhanced Permeability and Retention (EPR) effect, the signature of solid tumors with leaky vasculature and impaired lymphatic drainage. Nanocarriers between 10–200 nm in size can passively load into tumor tissues via these pathological vessels [48]. This method does not involve surface modification or the use of targeting ligands but depends solely on the anatomical and physiological uniqueness of the tumor compared to normal tissue. Although passive targeting has been successful in preclinical models, it is limited in clinical applications because of the heterogeneity of the EPR effect and variability in tumor vascularization [49].

6.2 Active Targeting via Ligands (Folate, Peptides, Antibodies)

Active targeting maximizes the specificity of nanocarrier delivery by the inclusion of ligands that bind to overexpressed receptors on cancer cells or the tumor microenvironment. Targeting

ligands used are folic acid, RGD peptides, aptamers, and monoclonal antibodies that bind to receptors such as Folate Receptor, Integrins, or HER2 [50]. These ligands mediate receptor-mediated endocytosis, which results in increased cellular uptake and drug internalization. Active targeting supports passive accumulation and enhances therapeutic effectiveness and lowers off-target effects. It is extensively utilized in the formation of next-generation smart nanocarriers [51].

6.3 Cell-Mediated and Biomimetic Approaches

Cell-mediated and biomimetic targeting approaches employ biological elements like immune cells, stem cells, or RBC-derived, cancer cell-derived, or platelet-derived membranes to hide or direct nanocarriers. The nanocarriers imitate the inherent processes of the body, with improved biocompatibility, immune avoidance, and targeting specificity [52]. For example, macrophage-coated nanoparticles can target inflamed tumor sites, whereas cancer

cell membrane-coated nanocarriers can provide homotypic targeting. These sophisticated strategies are the leading edge of targeted drug delivery, providing extended circulation, low immunogenicity, and specific tumor concentration [53].

7. RECENT ADVANCES AND CASE STUDIES

The clinical application of smart nanocarriers for site-specific chemotherapy has been significantly advanced over the last ten years. Several platforms have moved from bench studies to preclinical models and even to clinical assessments [54]. These developments highlight the power of stimulus-responsive nanocarriers to improve the effectiveness and safety of cancer therapy. This

section emphasizes approved or clinical-stage nanocarrier platforms, encouraging preclinical results, and practical examples of smart pH- or enzyme-responsive formulations [55].

7.1 Approved or Clinical-Stage Smart Nanocarriers

A few of the intelligent nanocarriers have advanced to the levels of clinical evaluation, and a few have even gained regulatory clearance. For example, ThermoDox®, a heat-sensitive liposome of doxorubicin, has been evaluated in combination with radiofrequency ablation. Doxil®, while not being stimuli-responsive, has set the stage for more intelligent liposomal constructions. Intelligent nanocarriers containing PEGylation, target ligands, or pH-sensitive elements are under investigation in clinical trials for multiple cancers. These clinical-stage carriers demonstrate improved safety profiles, enhanced drug accumulation at tumor sites, and promising therapeutic responses[56].

Nanocarrier System	Stimulus Sensitivity	Cancer Type	Clinical Status	Key Outcomes
ThermoDox®	Temperature-sensitive	Liver cancer	Clinical trials	Improved localized drug release with heat
pH-sensitive PLGA nanoparticles	pH-responsive	Breast cancer	Preclinical	Enhanced tumor targeting, increased efficacy
MMP-sensitive polymeric micelles	Enzyme-responsive	Various solid tumors	Preclinical	Better tumor penetration, reduced toxicity
Redox-sensitive PAMAM dendrimers	Redox-responsive	Lung and breast cancer	Preclinical	Efficient intracellular drug release
Gold nanoparticle-based carriers	External light-triggered	Multiple tumor types	Experimental	Combined photothermal and chemo therapy

7.2 Preclinical Models and Experimental Outcomes

An extensive array of preclinical evaluations using mice, rats, and zebrafish models

have established the therapeutic efficacy of stimuli-responsive nanocarriers for the regression of tumors. pH-sensitive polymeric micelles, redox-responsive dendrimers, and enzyme-sensitive liposomes

have been found to possess increased accumulation, rapid cellular uptake, and better cytotoxicity over traditional systems [57]. As a point of illustration, pH-sensitive PLGA nanoparticles containing paclitaxel exhibited enhanced antitumor activity in breast cancer mouse models.

Preclinical results also assist in assessing pharmacokinetics, biodistribution, and toxicity—key parameters prior to clinical transition [58].

7.3 Case Examples of pH/Enzyme-Sensitive Systems

pH-responsive nanocarriers are engineered to release drugs in the acidic tumor microenvironment (pH ~6.5–6.8) or within lysosomes (pH ~5.0). One of the most popular techniques includes the use of acid-cleavable linkers such as hydrazone or cis-aconityl groups. DOX-loaded pH-responsive liposomes, for instance, exhibited controlled release in acid tumor microenvironments.

Enzyme-responsive systems aim at overexpressed enzymes such as matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) or cathepsins, and peptide linkers cleaved by these enzymes. A good example is MMP-sensitive micelles used to deliver paclitaxel with increased penetration and decreased off-target toxicity. Such systems demonstrate accuracy in both drug release timing and site, enhancing treatment outcomes [42].

8. TOXICITY, SAFETY, AND REGULATORY CONSIDERATIONS

Although smart nanocarriers hold tremendous potential for targeted chemotherapy, their clinical acceptance depends on safety, tolerability,

and regulatory approval. Nanocarriers engage with the biological system in a distinctive way, generating anxiety regarding long-term toxicity, off-target toxicity, and metabolic disposition.

Regulatory authorities require extensive scrutiny of these materials prior to use in humans. This section discusses the key issues of biocompatibility, safety evaluation, regulatory issues, and measures to minimize unwanted toxicity [54].

8.1 Biocompatibility and Degradability

Biocompatibility protects nanocarriers from causing toxic immune reactions or injuring normal tissues. The best carriers should be non-immunogenic, non-toxic, and break down into innocuous byproducts. PLGA, PEG, chitosan, and lipid-based systems are widely used due to their safety profiles. Circulation time and clearance are also governed by biodegradability, an important factor to prevent deposition in critical organs such as the liver or spleen. Surface properties, charge, and size need to be optimized cautiously to minimize cytotoxicity while ensuring therapeutic efficacy [59].

8.2 Regulatory Hurdles for Nanomedicines

Intelligent nanocarriers are confronted with intricate regulatory issues by virtue of their hybrid nature (drug-device combinations) and unique mechanisms. Regulators such as the FDA and EMA demand rich data on pharmacokinetics, toxicity, manufacturing reproducibility, and quality control. Reproducibility in large-scale manufacture and full awareness of nanocarrier interactions with biological systems are also

essential. Diversity in global regulatory schemes and absence of standardized guidelines can hinder translation to the clinic. Regulatory approval usually requires other characterization methods like dynamic light scattering, zeta potential, and stability testing [60].

8.3 Strategies to Minimize Off-Target Effects

Off-target effects continue to be a major issue in nanomedicine, which can result in systemic toxicity or immunogenic responses. Stealth technologies such as PEGylation are employed to extend circulation and avoid immune recognition. Active targeting ligands increase specificity by interacting with tumor-specific receptors, reducing the amount of drug accumulated in normal tissues. Surface modification with biomimetic materials such as cell membranes decreases immune clearance even further. In addition, stimuli-responsive release systems facilitate activation of drugs only at the site of the tumor to minimize systemic exposure and side effects [61].

9. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

In spite of the fast-evolving smart nanocarriers for chemotherapy, many limitations prevent them from achieving their full clinical potential. Overcoming biological barriers, manufacturing challenges, and incorporating emerging technologies such as AI and theranostics is vital to future advancement. This section discusses major challenges and describes emerging trends and strategies that may define the next generation of precision nanomedicine [62].

9.1 Overcoming Biological Barriers

One of the greatest challenges is the effective delivery of nanocarriers across biological barriers like the bloodstream, endothelial barriers, extracellular matrix (ECM), and cell membranes. Tumor microheterogeneity, perfusion deficiency, and interstitial hypertension can hamper penetration and delivery. Evolved solutions involve switchable carriers, incorporation of ECM-degrading enzymes, and surface modification for improved permeability. Responsive multifunctional systems operating in response to extracellular and intracellular stimuli can enhance targeted release with reduced systemic loss [63].

9.2 Scale-Up and Commercialization Issues

Scaling up from lab-scale nanocarrier formulations to commercial products is challenging. Issues such as batch-to-batch uniformity, scalability of production processes, and economical manufacturing are difficult to address. Regulatory demands call for high-quality control over particle size, surface charge, and stability. Preservation of physicochemical properties during scale-up can also prove to be challenging, particularly for complicated hybrid or biomimetic systems. Aids such as automated microfluidic synthesis, lyophilization processes, and modular design approaches can provide reproducibility and economic viability [64].

9.3 Integration with AI and Theranostics

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and theranostics (therapy + diagnostics) are transforming cancer therapy by facilitating individualized, real-time decision-making. AI can select the best nanocarrier

design, forecast pharmacokinetics, and inform formulation based on tumor type. Theranostic nanocarriers integrate imaging probes with drugs to enable concurrent diagnosis, drug delivery, and treatment monitoring. The combination of AI-informed modeling with stimuli-responsive nanocarriers has potential to realize truly intelligent drug systems that can adjust to dynamic biology as well as patient-specific conditions [65].

CONCLUSION

Intelligent nanocarriers are a revolutionary breakthrough in targeted chemotherapy, with the potential to eliminate numerous pitfalls of conventional anti-cancer therapies. Leveraging the distinctive characteristics of the tumor microenvironment—e.g., acidic pH, hypoxia, and excess enzyme activity—these platforms allow for targeted, regulated drug delivery directly at the cancer location, reducing systemic toxicity and maximizing therapeutic effect. Stimuli-responsive platforms such as pH-, enzyme-, redox-, and hypoxia-sensitive carriers have been of particular promise within preclinical and initial clinical settings. Despite encouraging outcomes, problems exist in converting these advanced systems into common clinical applications. Challenges pertaining to biological barriers, mass production, regulatory clearance, and safety need to be overcome by interdisciplinary innovation and strict testing. In addition, the combination of intelligent nanocarriers with artificial intelligence and theranostic technologies can lead to fully personalized and adaptive

cancer treatment.

As science continues to evolve, ongoing innovation in multifunctional, biocompatible, and cost-effective smart nanocarriers will be critical to unlocking their full clinical potential. Ultimately, they have the promise of not just improving therapeutic outcomes but also transforming our approach to cancer treatment in an era of precision medicine.

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